

Identity Document Generation using QR Code Technology

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Abstract: QR code stands for Quick response code which is a two dimensional matrix barcode used for storing encoded data. The data stored can be decoded by scanning them using a barcode scanner. Different ID proofs are necessary for all the Indians for different government related purposes. Sometimes, we may not have the appropriate identity document with us when we approach a government organization to fulfill our need. In order to overcome this problem, in this paper we propose a method to integrate the customer identity documents to generate a QR code which will be unique to each user. The data stored in the QR code can be retrieved with the help of a QR code scanner. After scanning, the data about the customer can be viewed and can be downloaded according to their needs. In this system, we used Python libraries to generate encrypted QR code.

Keywords: Encryption, QR code, Decryption, identity documents

I. INTRODUCTION

QR code technology was introduced in 1994 by Masahiro Hara from a Japanese automotive company named Denso Wave. It comprises of encoding, storing and decoding of data. It has significant advantages in data types, data capacity, data density, data acquisition, and data recovery capability.

One of the practical uses of QR code technology is for payment. Another is for joining a Wi-Fi network. A third is for counterfeit detection. A fourth is for passenger control.

This system's primary goal is to convert user sensitive information into a QR code that can be read by reading software. This study addresses the issue, taking into account the consumers' predominance of ID proofs. The mentioned problem can be solved using an all-in-one QR code user identification.

One QR card can include all of the user's private information which is produced using other government-approved IDs. The system will be more beneficial to the users in all aspects. Any information connected to a specific consumer can be easily retrieved.

II. STRUCTURE OF QR CODE

Figure 1: QR code structure

In the end, the QR code became a standard after being developed in Japan. It has been approved as a standard by the International Organization for Standardization (ISO), the Japanese Industrial Standards (JIS), and the Association for Automatic Identification and Mobility (AIM).

As seen in the accompanying graphic, every QR code has an encoding region and function patterns (Fig 1). Separator, finder, timing, and alignment patterns are examples of function patterns. The QR code has finder patterns in its three corners, which are used to make it easier to determine its size, location, and inclination. The patterns can be read using imaging devices like camera, mobile phones, and scanners and is processed using Reed-Solomon error correction. When scanned, the unique pattern present on QR code is translated into human-readable data. The

conventional QR code has 40 versions each having different number of data modules. As version number increases, the number of data modules present in QR code also increases. QR code uses Reed-Solomon algorithm, the oldest and widely used algorithm which enables them to be scanned even if a certain amount of code is blocked or covered up. In contrast to solitary cases, it enables the correction of faults identified in bursts.

Versions 1 through 40 of the QR Code symbology are available. Versions differs with number of data modules.

Figure 2 : Version 1

Figure 3: Version 40

III. MOTIVATION

This work aims to introduce a more sophisticated mechanism by encoding the confidential data that enables customer identification more secure without the need for any other identification documents. The confidential data of each individual is encoded in the form of QR code so that it will be more secure. The user data or documents can be retrieved by scanning the QR code using image scanning devices which includes mobile phones, barcode or QR code scanners etc.

IV. LITERATURE REVIEW

This section studies about the existing system. QR codes are introduced for keeping the data in encoded form and for fast reading applications.

Students use QR codes extensively, particularly for academic purposes. It is simpler to use a smartphone

camera to scan a QR code than to manually enter a link in a variety of instructional processes. Additionally, we can include it in advertising materials. It is quite easy to create a QR code [1].

Advanced partitioning algorithms were used in a novel way to increase security [2]. Filtering, grayscale binarization, distortion correction, inverse transformation, and perspective projection are all parts of the preprocessing process. The image is filtered using an enhanced adaptive median filter algorithm, and the distortion is corrected using a BP neural network-based distortion correction technique [3]. Due to several factors, such as size variations, orientation, style, alignment, and other factors complicated backgrounds and low image contrast, the recognition of QR codes from photos is a difficult task. Preprocessing an image before it is used, geometric correction, tilt correction, segmentation, and localization, image normalization, classification, and Feature Extraction were employed as methods of pattern extraction [4].

In an effort to improve the digital security situation, the notion of digital authentication by QR code was implemented in the digital education system [5]. Conference poster presentations can significantly increase their effect by using QR codes. Movies can focus attention, efficiently communicate information, simplify complicated concepts, and trigger emotions, all of which are likely to promote retention. Evidence has demonstrated that learners' performance increases when using videos as adjuvant teaching material². A QR code enables conference attendees to access movies that speakers have linked to their posters in place of putting images on a poster [6]. In several industries during the epidemic, particularly the NHS Track and Trace and NHS COVID-19 applications, QR codes have been essential [7]. The literature has a variety of different proposals for computerized consumer verification systems. The fact that many of them do not offer an adequate encryption or decryption mechanism results in the leakage of consumer data.

V. PROPOSED SYSTEM

The systematic use of QR code is to store and download the associated information because of its high authentication and security. We propose an advanced concept to enhance the security of the ID proofs and eliminate the need to carry all the identity documents of the customers. To use this, all the government ID proofs of an individual is integrated to form a unique identification string which will be then converted to an encrypted form using the python library called fernet. Python programmers may easily include encryption an authentication into their programs using Fernet. The Python module Fernet, part of the Cryptography package, encrypts and decrypts data using a special key. The encrypted form of the concatenated string is then used to generate its corresponding QR code. The two main methods used by the

fernet package are encrypt, which is for converting original text into cipher text and decrypt, which is to convert cipher text into its original form. The fernet module ensures that information encrypted with it cannot be changed or decrypted without the key. The data of each those individual can be retrieved by scanning the generated QR code. The suggested method does away with the requirement to carry around several identity cards for a variety of user authentication requirements. The proposed system of QR code can be used in government organizations or agencies and various other industries including banking, health care, education, shopping and entertainment.

```
1 import qrcode
2 from cryptography.fernet import Fernet
3
4
5 qr_object = qrcode.QRCode(
6     version = 30,
7     error_correction = qrcode.constants.ERROR_CORRECT_L,
8     box_size = 10,
9     border = 4,
10 )
11
12
13 ID1=input("Enter PAN NUMBER : ")
14 ID2=input("Enter DRIVING LICENCE NUMBER : ")
15 IntegratedID=ID1+ID2
16
```

Figure 4 (a): Creating objects and allowing user input

```
17 key = Fernet.generate_key()
18 fernet = Fernet(key)
19 encryptedID = fernet.encrypt(IntegratedID.encode())
20 print("Concatenated Value: ", IntegratedID)
21 print("Encrypted Value: ", encryptedID)
22 qr_object.add_data(encryptedID)
23 qr_object.make(fit = True)
24 qr_image = qr_object.make_image(fill_color = "black", back_color = "white")
25 qr_image.save("IDqr.png")
26
27 qr_image.show()
28
```

Figure 4 (b): Concatenating IDs and encryption process

In the above figure, QR code is generated by importing the python library 'qrcode' which is then used to create QR code object. Four parameters are passed in to create the object, the first of which is the version of the QR code that will be generated. error correction level is described in paragraph two. The options are L, M, Q, or H. (3) box size – determines how many pixels each QR code "box" is. (4) Border—This setting determines how many boxes the border should be. (4 is the default value).

VI. RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

During the experiment, the unique numbers of each identity card is concatenated and a single string is generated. The resulted value is converted into cipher text using an

appropriate encryption algorithm. The experiment is carried out in Windows 11, using Visual Studio Code. Python has a library called "qrcode" which is used for generating QR code images . qrcode library is installed using the below command.

```
pip install qrcode
```

```
pip install cryptography
```

Steps:

- Create an instance of QRCode class
- Add data to the instance using add_data() function
- Encode data using make() function
- Create image using make_image() function

```
Enter PAN NUMBER : JDNYU7887H
Enter DRIVING LICENCE NUMBER : KL032018000132
```

Figure 5: The proposed system's input

Figure 6: The proposed system's output

VII. CONCLUSION

The proposed system discusses the encoding of user identity data to QR code to make the confidential data more secure and hidden from the outside world. With the aid of a scanning device, to read encoded information about the item on which it is printed, utilize a QR code. These days, QR codes are an effective marketing tool. Numerous uses for QR-Codes exist, including content linkage, object identification, time tracking, product tracking, and time tracking. In the upcoming years, it will still be applicable. While the COVID-19 epidemic was ongoing, they gained enormous popularity. The fact that QR codes are affordable, widely applicable, and will help you quickly and simply access the desired information makes them more welcoming. Given its effectiveness and convenience, unless a new revolutionary technology supersedes it, QR Code usage will only continue to grow. In python, we can customize a QR code using QRCode having parameters-version, error_correction, box_size and border. The functions of the object QRCode used to create a QR code are: add_data (), make(), and make_image(). We have

proposed a system that takes the unique identity number of each individual as a string and concatenate then to form a unique identification number which will be then encrypted using the fernet module, which has inbuilt functions for encryption and decryption, provided by library to encrypt the string to encode it in the form of a QR code.

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